

CAREER STAGES AND KEYS TO SUCCESS FOR TOURISM INDUSTRY MANAGERS

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ABSTRACT

The manager's career path takes effort and time. This study aims to identify the career stages of a manager from the staff level to finally reach the management level. This study records the career stages of managers at all levels of management, from first-line managers to top managers. The required competencies and keys to success based on the experience of managers are explained further in this study. This study analyzes the key to success for managers to reach the management level in the tourism industry. The tourism industry in Bali as a research sample by observing and interviewing 100 tourism industry managers who are currently in management rank (first, middle, and top line). This type of research is a qualitative research conducted with data collection techniques through direct observation, in-depth interviews, and distributing questionnaires. Data analysis used descriptive qualitative and the sample was purposive sampling. The research implication reveals that the principles adopted by industrial managers are the strongest internal motivation in achieving success in the industrial world. Originality/value based on the literature reviewed, a list of key success factors in the tourism industry sector was compiled and the lack of similar research on this topic

Keywords: Career, Manager, Tourism, Industry

1. INTRODUCTION

HR is an employee who is ready, capable, and alert to achieving organizational goals. HR is a very important resource in an organization. Because HR has an active role in carrying out and realizing organizational goals and decision-making processes. Professional HR management arrangements are needed because they can work productively. Professional employee management starts as early as possible, since employee recruitment, selection, classification, and placement of employees according to abilities, skills, and development must be (Werther and Davis, 1996; Sutrisno, 2010). The training and development aim to prepare managers and employees in forming professionalism and having a global mindset to be able to become career strategists in facing the challenges that occur.

The steps that must be taken in dealing with the challenges that occur are (Barner, 1994; Miswanto, 2005): 1) Managers and employees must keep up with trends in the business and economic world that may provide growth opportunities for potential career paths; 2) Managers and employees develop a clear view or picture based on career and lifestyle needs; 3) Managers and employees must benchmark their expertise by using the best expertise in the same field now and in the future; 4) Managers and employees form a contingency plan to be able to have a career in conditions that are constantly changing and uncertain; 5) Managers and employees develop portable skills, not just relying on contextual skills. Portable skills are skills that can be transferred easily to other different work environments. Portable skills include managerial

skills, intellectual skills, communication skills, and interpersonal skills. On the other hand, contextual skills are relatively non-transferable skills that are used in different work environments.

The success of the industry and its ultimate goal depends on the quality of Human Resources (HR) (Gruescu et al., 2008; Dissanayake and Nandasena, 2019). The real HR challenge for the tourism industry is to recruit and retain employees with the right skills, knowledge, and attitudes for their jobs. The industry faces various challenges to find and maintain its competitive advantage as a differentiator between companies in the availability of resources (Bednarska, 2013; Bashir and Verma, 2017). On the other hand, the tourism industry also offers various job opportunities, careers, and very promising management positions. HR is a determining factor for the success of the company considering that it is the executive, regulator, and decision-maker in the company. On the other hand, individuals exercise control over their careers, so that career development will move from the employee organization. This condition places emphasis on the individual's ability to develop the game. Career management includes planning and developing individual and organizational careers (Rivai and Sagala, 2009; Pangestu, 2012). Career planning and development are provided not to ensure the career success of employees, but also to assist employees in matters related to work, assignments, and organizational decisions, both inside and outside the organization. Career planning is hard work that will pay off so that its function as a tool to generate motivation can be achieved. Career planning can also facilitate senior employees to pass on their experience and knowledge to their juniors.

Macroeconomic theory shows that economic growth is accompanied by changes in the distribution of output and the structure of the economy, an increase in the contribution of the industrial and service sectors, as well as an increase in the education and skills of the workforce. Regional economic growth can be obtained from increasing capital through public investment and savings, increasing the quality and quantity of labor through increasing knowledge and skills, and improving technology in the production process. The demand for the production of goods and services will increase the use of production input factors. One of the important production input factors is labor. Increased production capacity can encourage job creation and the use of labor. The industry continues to seek and find its human resource talents to improve company performance and productivity. HR is a very valuable asset for companies that continue to improve their knowledge, skills, and competencies through the latest pieces of training in the current digital economy era by the required qualifications. Companies are required to be able to build a competitive advantage in their human resources which aim to provide benefits for the company. The tourism industry is a company whose products are mostly in the form of services and or a combination of goods and services that causes the tourism industry products to be very specific, thus requiring special knowledge about the sector. Before the Corona Virus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic, UNWTO noted the industry and consideration of 1 in 10 workers. International tourist arrivals increased from 25 million globally in 1950 to 278 million in 1980, 674 million in 2000, and 1.235 million in 2016. Similarly, international tourism receipts from destinations around the world jumped from the US. \$2 billion in 1950 to US\$ 104 billion in 1980, US\$ 495 billion in 2000, and US\$ 1,220

billion in 2016 (UNWTO, 2017). International tourism represents 7 percent of the world's exports of goods and services, an increase of one percent from 6 percent in 2015. The tourism industry has grown more rapidly over the past five years. As a worldwide export category, it ranks third after chemicals and fuels and ahead of automotive and food products. In many developing countries, tourism is the top export category.

But in 2020 there will be a disturbing and unfortunate incidence of new diseases among the more than 30 new infections the world has experienced in 30 years (Nkengasong, 2020; Kausal and Srivastava, 2021). This time the nomenclature given to the new Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS) is the new coronavirus (COVID-19). The disease is atypical pneumonia that started in China and then spread to countries around the world. The countries of the United States, Brazil, India, Italy, Spain, France, South Korea, Iran, and many more experienced the unprecedented spread of disease and loss of life in recent months. The impact of the coronavirus outbreak to date has exceeded the impact observed during the SARS epidemic in 2002 (Causal and Srivastava, 2021). The health crisis that occurred developed into an economic and social crisis with a global impact. The tourism industry has been heavily impacted as an industry based on mobility and closed human interaction with the COVID-19 pandemic (Gallen, 2020; Hao et al., 2020).

This research was conducted in Bali a tourist destination that has unique natural and cultural beauty. Bali has also been named the Best Island of the Destin Asian Readers Choice Awards for 12 consecutive years, and as a Trip Advisor Destination version of the World's Best 2017 (Bali Provincial Statistics Agency, 2018). Bali has an important role in national tourism. The arrival of foreign tourists to Bali in the last 5 years has increased quite rapidly, recorded from 3.3 million people in 2013 to 5.7 million foreign tourists in 2017. Overall, foreign tourist arrivals increased by 15.62 percent from 2015. 2016 to 2017. This increase in the number of foreign tourists is lower than the increase in foreign tourists from 2015 to 2016 which reached 23.14 percent (Bali Province Central Statistics Agency, 2018). The number of tourists will directly increase the category of accommodation and food and drink services. Bali The number of accommodations in Bali reaches 4,924 accommodations with a total of 84,414 rooms consisting of five-star hotels, budget hotels, and tourist lodges. The number of restaurants in 2018 reached 2,518 restaurants spread across districts/cities in Bali (Bali Province Central Statistics Agency, 2018). This has a significant impact on the Balinese economy.

In the province of Bali, employment issues are still a complicated phenomenon. Moreover, the labor market in Bali is expected to be more integrated in the future. Bali is an area that is easily accessible from anywhere. The result is clear, the flow of migration and urbanization becomes inevitable. However, this situation will have an impact on the structure of employment, which is likely to increase the population of productive age. Therefore, the expansion of job opportunities must be optimized productively (productive employment). The population is a development asset if it can be empowered optimally. Even so, it can become a development burden if it is not accompanied by an adequate quality of population (HR) in the regions. The more developed the hospital industry today, the greater the competition among others, this of course has an impact on the improvement in the field of employment, especially the

improvement and development of adequate human resources. This study records the career stages of managers at all levels of management, from first-line managers to top managers. The required competencies and keys to success based on the experience of managers are described further in this study.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research is qualitative research conducted with data collection techniques through direct observation, in-depth interviews, and distributing questionnaires. The presentation of the results of data analysis can be done, either formally (in tabular form) or informally (in narrative form). The research began with the distribution of questionnaires and in-depth interviews regarding the career stages of tourism industry managers, the competencies needed in career stages, and the keys to success for tourism industry managers. This study uses a purposive sampling technique for as many as 100 tourism industry managers, both at the lower, middle and upper levels. This research was analyzed using the Qualitative Descriptive Analysis technique. The qualitative descriptive technique is the process of compiling data, organizing it into a pattern, category, and basic description, or the process of organizing and sorting data into patterns, categories, and basic descriptions so that themes can be found that can be formulated.

3. RESULTS

The results describe the characteristics of respondents, career stages of tourism industry managers, competencies needed in career stages, and keys to success for tourism industry managers. Respondents in this study amounted to 100 people who are at the management level in the tourism industry, both accommodation, restaurants, and travel agents. The profile of respondents based on age is known to be 20.00 percent in their 20s; 24.00 percent at the age of 30 years; 30.00 percent at the age of 40 years; and 27.00 percent at the age of 50 years. Based on the results of research in the 1950s, some of them were at the top management level. Although there are respondents who occupy the top management level at a young age (20s) because they choose to have a career and open their own business. Meanwhile, middle management positions are mostly occupied by respondents in their 30s.

The profile of respondents by gender shows that 28.00 percent are female and 72.00 percent are male. Based on observations, it is known that the majority of employees occupying the management level are male. This is strongly influenced by the culture and daily activities in Bali which adheres to a patrilineal system. The role of men in the family household in Bali as breadwinners, and Balinese women as housewives, raising children, and carrying out community customs and or helping to earn a living. The intensity of Balinese women's activities in carrying out cultural customs in daily life, said Balinese women tend to put careers at work aside.

Table 1 Respondent Profile

No.	Category	Options	Total (person)	Percent (%)
1	Ages	21-30 years old	20	20.00
		31-40 years old	24	24.00
		41-50 years old	30	30.00
		51-60 years old	27	27.00
2.	Gender	Male	72	72.00
		Female	28	28.00
3.	Level of Education	Diploma	75	75.00
		Bachelor	22	22.00
		Master	3	3.00

The profile of the respondents based on the level of education is known that 74.00 percent are diplomas; 23.00 percent are undergraduate and only 3.00 percent masters. The level of education in the tourism industry is dominated by diploma graduates, both diplomas 1, 2 and diploma 3. If it is related to the age of the respondents, the majority of respondents aged 30 years and over have diploma education, while the age of respondents 20 years old and in their 30s varies between diplomas and undergraduate. This is also supported by the limited number of educational institutions that offer tourism undergraduate programs in Bali. However, of the total respondents, it is known that not all of them have a tourism education background.

Career Stages of Tourism Industry Manager

On the career ladder, managers working in the tourism industry in Bali noted that most (92.00 percent) started at the staff level, even 12 of the total respondents did not work directly but became daily workers before becoming staff. Only 8.00 percent directly occupy the management level. This is because there are opportunities and vacant positions in the tourism industry where managers start their careers. In addition, there are respondents who from the beginning wanted to be entrepreneurs, so they opened their businesses in the field of travel agents. Based on the respondent's length of service as staff, it takes an average of 7 years to occupy the first line management/lower manager level. Respondents who have occupied the first-line management level/lower manager require an average of 3 years to occupy the middle management level, while respondents who occupy the middle management level require an average of 15 years to occupy the top management level. Career stages in the tourism industry are strongly influenced by internal conditions within themselves and the external conditions of the respondents. Internal conditions are based on knowledge and skills controlled by managers. The knowledge referred to here is the knowledge required per the competencies required by the job and by the standard operating procedures set by the company. The skills needed by respondents at each level of management are different, although in general most stated that interpersonal skills and managerial skills are needed so that they can carry out their jobs well. At the first/lower line manager level, technical skills are needed, because respondents at this level must provide examples and direct supervision. However, at the middle and upper management levels, the emphasis is on managerial skills especially on motivating subordinates; leadership abilities, communication skills, and experience. Other things that are considered very important by employees that affect their careers are teamwork, mastering several foreign

languages, mastering information and computer technology, product knowledge, and training provided by the company. In some jobs that require art such as restaurant chefs, employees state that it is important to foster innovation and creativity. In addition, some mention that time management and an open attitude to receive criticism are important inputs for their progress. The external conditions of employees are strongly influenced by the culture of the organization in which they work. The organizational culture that is formed greatly affects the atmosphere and work environment, thus making them comfortable at work. In addition, career paths are also strongly influenced by vacant positions and the promotion system adopted by the company. Several complaints were made by respondents when determining the management level based on ability, not seniority. Sometimes older subordinates have less respect for younger bosses. Most of the respondents also stated that another challenge is working under pressure. The pressure in question is accountability to superiors, sales targets to be achieved, and professionalism at work. Other challenges are also expressed in the form of creating a conducive work environment, increasing discipline, and consistency in implementing the rules that have been set in the company/organization. The keys to success presented by the managers of the tourism industry, especially in the current digital economy era which is full of business competition, include:

(1) Experience

Experience managers are the best teachers. Experience often teaches them something very valuable, which they don't get when they study at school/university. Experience in several companies/hotels/restaurants can take them to the top management level. They also stated that the experience does not always have to experience the event itself, but also wanting to learn from the experiences of others is very helpful.

(2) Hard work

Managers state that they put in hard work, resilience, and an unyielding attitude to realize their goals. Without the hard work of others, they believe that they cannot succeed in fulfilling their dreams. The attitude of hard work that is relentless and always loves what they do makes what they do maximally and without burden.

(3) Have skills

The scope of the new job and related requirements has been limited following the division into individual booking and vacation design, guided tours, business travel organization, and travel agency support. The project identified the following complex new skill sets: (1) travel designer, online travel agent, and event designer in holiday booking and design; (2) tour representatives for limited mobility, guest relations, and live and representative travel services; (3) business travel managers for business travel organizations; (4) agent consultant for travel agent support. Managers are expected to possess the following skills and competencies: computer skills, business, and strategic planning, strategic alliances, management skills, management through vision and values, results in management, accounting, product development, innovation, HR management, objectives management, project management, management skills for overcoming the effects of globalization,

change management, marketing, and sales skills (EC, 2001: 26). The special skill conveyed by the manager is the mastery of technology in the current era of the digital economy, considering that most of the company's product reservation and promotion activities are online. In the tourism industry, the internet offers the potential to make information and booking facilities available to large numbers of tourists at a relatively low cost. It also provides a tool for communication between tourism suppliers, intermediaries, and end consumers. The Internet is revolutionizing the distribution of tourism information and sales. More and more internet users are buying online and tourism will get a bigger share of the online commerce market. In addition, other skills that are conveyed are foreign language skills and communication skills play an important role. Communication competence is conceptualized as an individual's ability to adapt effectively to his environment over time (Spitzberg & Cupach, 1984; Oktadiana and Djauhari, 2011). A key feature of this definition is the focus on adaptability, which has been widely accepted as a component of communication competence. Thus, in a culturally diverse workplace, competence in intercultural communication can be described as the ability to be flexible and adaptable to different cultural contexts, i.e. be sensitive to cultural situations and act accordingly.

(4) Mastering science

The knowledge gained during education at school or in college is considered very useful for managers in carrying out their duties in the industrial world. Educational programs are expected to meet the changing needs of entrepreneurs, new technologies, and alternative forms of service (Sakharchuk et al., 2013). Likewise, the training that is followed while working in the company can increase the understanding and work efficiency of managers.

(5) Discipline

Discipline is a person's behavior that is shown by being obedient and obedient to the obligations or duties he carries to achieve organizational or company goals. High discipline has implications for increasing work productivity as indicated by the achievement of good, effective, and efficient results, attitude and accuracy in work, and satisfactory quantity and quality of work.

(6) Willingness to learn

The willingness to learn ability is considered very important for tourism actors considering the tourism industry is very dynamic which forces a person to continue to adapt and continue to learn during changes that occur from time to time. The existence of a high willingness to learn, then a person can face the changes that occur, and update the information and abilities that are needed to support the career and progress of the company.

(7) Information network and cooperation

Information is the lifeblood of tourism (Poon, 1993). Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has a huge impact on the tourism industry. ICT enables direct communication with clients and increases the efficiency and effectiveness of customer

service, trade, and processes related to product design. At the same time, ICT makes the competition tougher and demands constant investment. The use of technology can help the tourism sector face several challenges, including direct ordering, product marketing, branding, and so on. Likewise with cooperation. Cooperation is very necessary because it can provide benefits and open up opportunities for the progress of the company or organization. Cooperation can be done internally or externally to the company or organization.

(8) Teamwork

In an organization, it is not necessary to have a superman, but a superteam who can overcome various work challenges together. Job specifications between teams can increase effectiveness and efficiency at work. Forming a solid team is not an easy matter for the tourism industry manager, because it requires the implementation of management functions at every level of work. Another challenge they face is the varying abilities and understanding of employees towards the organization and organizational goals. Different motivations and personal approaches for each employee are needed, so it forces managers to always think creatively in creating a strong team.

(9) Have commitment

For managers, commitment is very important because it helps them to stay motivated and move following organizational goals. Managers also strive to continue to increase the loyalty of their employees from time to time with various awards for those who excel and punishment for those who violate. Appreciation can be in the form of selecting outstanding employees every month, quarterly, and annually. In addition, the implementation of promotions and employee capacity building is a scheduled agenda that is applied to the tourism industry.

(10) Responsible

For managers, taking responsibility is an opportunity rather than a burden. For them, responsibility is an opportunity to show the real quality of their work.

In addition to the top ten things stated, respondents also stated other keys to success, namely: focus and perseverance, creativity and innovation, integrity, adaptability, customer orientation, respect and respect for others, and high morale.

4. DISCUSSION

The effectiveness of a manager is seen in his ability to move his subordinates/staff. Because the performance of a manager depends on the performance and productivity of his subordinates. Managers in carrying out their duties and responsibilities face many challenges. The challenges faced by a manager come from within company and from outside the company. Most of the respondents stated that the biggest challenge for managers is HR in the company, especially staff who are subordinates. Lazy staff, lack of discipline, difficulty giving sanctions, communication disorders, and difficulty motivating subordinates are often conveyed by

managers. The next challenge is to address tourist/customer complaints which must be resolved with good solutions. If tourist/customer complaints are not handled properly, with external challenges in the form of competition (similar products/companies) in the tourism industry in Bali, customers tend to switch to competing products. This gives a negative image which results in a decrease in product sales. Most consumers always have higher expectations of the products they buy; Therefore, business people who can expect consumer needs more quickly and can develop their products more efficiently and effectively will be able to answer consumer needs in front of their competitors, and consumers will switch to the products and businesses of business actors (Oliver R, and Swan JE, 1989; Vargas, G., Cardenas, L. and Matarranz, L., 2000; Kozak, M. and Rimmington, M., 2000; Kerdpitak and Dusit, 2016).

Career development is the process of increasing individual work abilities that are achieved to achieve the desired career (Rivai and Sagala, 2009). The goal of all career development programs is to match the needs and goals of employees with the career opportunities available in the company today and in the future. Career development in an organization requires 2 main processes (Sulistiyan and Rosidah, 2009): 1) Career planning, namely the way people plan and realize their careers; and Career management, namely the way organizations design career programs for their employees.

This process is a formal, organized, and planned effort to strike a balance between individual career desires and the organization's workforce requirements. To facilitate the preparation, HR management can use two kinds of career paths (Sutrisno, 2010), namely: 1) Traditional career paths, namely the sequence is a combination of vertical upward movement (promotion or transfer to a position that has a higher level) and horizontal (transfer or transfer to a position that has the same level); 2) Innovative career path because the sequence is a combination of vertical upward, vertical downward movement (demotion or demotion to a lower level) and horizontal. If the goal is to reward HR performance, then the traditional career path is the right choice. Meanwhile, if the career development policy aims to provide the best possible experience and opportunity to HR before reaching the top position, then an innovative career path should be implemented. Career development is aimed at achieving gradual improvement by working harmoniously together to improve employee career competency. Personal competence reflects various forms of knowledge, and a good career reflects the application of these various forms of knowledge (Arthur et al., 1999; Pangestu, 2012). They categorize career competency into three types, namely: "knowing the cause", "knowing anyone", and "knowing how to do something". The first category relates to career motivation, personal meaning, and identification; the second category deals with career-relevant networks and relationships, and the third category deals with career-relevant skills and work-related knowledge. To improve employee career competency, a good relationship between company managers and company employees is needed. Viewed from the employee's point of view, good career management emphasizes the necessary personal qualities, and therefore career competency becomes something important for them. From the company's perspective, helping staff develop their careers and increase their career satisfaction is an effective way of attracting and retaining quality staff members (Arthur et al., 1999; Barnett and Bradley, 2007; Pangestu, 2012).

5. CONCLUSION

The tourism industry is a labor-intensive industry that provides various job opportunities, careers, and prospects for very promising management positions. HR must be viewed as a company asset that needs to be continuously improved in terms of knowledge, skills, and competencies through the latest training by the required qualifications. At the career level, managers who work in the tourism industry mostly start from the staff level. Career stages in the tourism industry are strongly influenced by internal conditions and external conditions. Internal conditions are based on knowledge and skills controlled by managers. At the first/lower line manager level, technical skills are needed, because respondents at this level must provide examples and direct supervision. However, at the middle and upper management levels, the emphasis is on managerial skills especially on motivating subordinates; leadership abilities, communication skills, and experience. The external conditions of employees are strongly influenced by the culture of the organization in which they work. The organizational culture that is formed greatly affects the atmosphere and work environment, thus making them comfortable at work. The keys to success for tourism industry managers include experience, hard work, skill, mastery of knowledge, discipline, willingness to learn, information networks and cooperation, teamwork, commitment, and responsibility.

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Conflict Of Interest

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.

Declaration of Interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper. The authors declare the following financial interests/personal.

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